

Efficacy of mycophenolate mofetil in the management of pemphigus vulgaris

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ABSTRACT

Pemphigus is one of the major vesiculobullous disease affecting the oral cavity. Systemic corticosteroids are the cornerstone of management in pemphigus; however, it has significant adverse effects. One of the more recent adjuvant therapies for pemphigus is mycophenolate mofetil. Combination of drug with corticosteroids helps to minimize steroid-induced potential systemic toxicities

This systematic review and meta-analysis is written and conducted according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA Statement) checklist Recommendations (10) and was registered on PROSPERO (protocol number # CRD42020197146). All the randomized control trials in which the treatment of pemphigus vulgaris with mycophenolate mofetil are mentioned. Assessment of risk of bias was conducted according to the guidance in Higgins, JPT, Green, S (editors): the Cochrane Handbook for systematic review of Interventions Versions 5.1,0 (updated March 2011) The Cochrane collaboration, 2011.

For complete healing of lesions, results showed insignificant effect of treatment, as indicated by p-values of 0.922 and 0.584 each for fixed and random effect. For remission of disease, fixed effect showed significant effect of treatment, as indicated by p-values of 0.008 and random effect showed insignificant effect of treatment with p-value of 0.149. For adverse effects, fixed effect showed insignificant effect of treatment, as indicated by p-values of 0.430 and random effect also showed insignificant effect of treatment with p-value of 0.980.

Mycophenolate mofetil is equally effective in the management of pemphigus vulgaris with complete remission and less adverse effects. So, it can be the potential agent in the management of pemphigus vulgaris.

KEYWORDS

Pemphigus, Mycophenolate mofetil, Corticosteroids, Systematic review

INTRODUCTION

Oral health is essential as it symbolizes the overall health, well-being and quality of life of an individual, thus oral cavity is rightly described as a mirror of general health or diseases.

Pemphigus is one of the major vesiculobullous disease affecting the oral cavity, which is characterized by the appearance of chronic multiple lesions.⁽¹⁾ Each of its type has distinct clinical and immunopathologic features. The word 'Pemphigus' is derived from the Greek word 'Pempnix' meaning 'Bubble' or 'Blister'.⁽²⁾ Pemphigus vulgaris, a variant of pemphigus is an autoimmune, intraepithelial blistering disease that frequently appears first in the oral cavity and can progress to involve the other sites.⁽³⁾

If left untreated, pemphigus vulgaris is associated with high mortality.⁽⁴⁾ The main aim of the management of the disease is to decrease blister formation, promote healing and suppression of blisters and erosions, determine the minimal dose of medication necessary to control the disease process so as to be effective over long term, have adequate patient compliance and ultimately withdrawal of treatment.⁽⁵⁾

The various treatment modalities available for pemphigus vulgaris has variable prognosis. Systemic corticosteroids are the cornerstone of management in pemphigus; however, its high-dose and prolonged courses for disease control are associated with significant adverse effects.⁽⁶⁾ Currently, the primary morbidity and mortality are due to the complications of treatment.⁽⁷⁾

Reduction of steroid use is a key goal in the development of new treatments.⁽⁸⁾ Therefore, there is a continued search for more effective and safe treatment protocols for patients with pemphigus. Presently available therapies are primarily directed against the formation of the antibodies, via the suppression of the immune system and reduction of adverse events. So, adjuvant therapies with immunosuppressive drugs such as azathioprine, mycophenolate mofetil, methotrexate and cyclophosphamide are recommended.

Among these, the purine analogue, azathioprine (AZA) was frequently the first choice of drug and has been established for years in the therapy of pemphigus.⁽⁹⁾ However, there are several reports regarding how azathioprine targets several cell populations and can account for more severe and extensive side effects.⁽⁹⁾

One of the more recent adjuvant therapies for pemphigus is mycophenolate mofetil.⁽¹⁰⁾ It is an ester of mycophenolic acid, which is the active metabolite which is shown to reduce the antibody titres to below detectable levels in the diseased patients.⁽¹¹⁾ Combination of drug with corticosteroids helps to lower initial steroid dose without relapse, faster reduction of steroid dose as well as much less final maintenance dose, thus, minimizing steroid-induced potential systemic toxicities.⁽¹⁰⁾ Compared to the most commonly used immunosuppressive agent, azathioprine, it has fewer side effects, and is non-mutagenic.⁽⁷⁾

This systematic review and meta-analysis aims to identify and interpret results of studies that evaluated the efficacy of mycophenolate mofetil in the management of pemphigus vulgaris and compare this entity with other treatment modalities.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This systematic review and meta-analysis is written and conducted according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA Statement) checklist Recommendations (10) and was registered on PROSPERO (International prospective register of systematic reviews) (protocol number # CRD42020197146).

Study design - All the randomized control trials in which the treatment of pemphigus vulgaris with mycophenolate mofetil are mentioned.

Selection criteria - Based on PRISMA statement flowchart.

Fig 1: Flow chart showing systematic literature search for the present review

Eligibility criteria - Based on PICO (population, intervention, comparators and outcomes)

Sr no.	Population	Intervention	Comparison	Outcome	Authors	Year
1	33 patients of pemphigus vulgaris and 7 patients of pemphigus foliaceus	2 mg/kg methylprednisolone with 2 g/d mycophenolate mofetil	2 mg/kg methylprednisolone with 2 mg/kg azathioprine sodium	Mycophenolate mofetil and azathioprine demonstrate similar efficacy, corticosteroid-sparing effects as adjuvants	Stefan Beisert, ; Thomas Werfel, Uta Frieling, Markus Bo`hm, Michael Sticherling, ; Rudolf Stadler, Detlev Zillikens, Berthold Rzany,; Nicolas Hunzelmann, Michael Meurer, Harald Gollnick,; Thomas Ruzicka, Hans Pillekamp,; Volker Junghans, Thomas A. Luger,	2006
2	120 active cases of pemphigus	2 mg/kg/day	2 mg/kg/day prednisolone	Mycophenolate mofetil was found	Cheyda Chams-Davatchi, , Nafiseh	2007

	vulgaris	prednisolone and 2 g/d mycophenolate mofetil (P/MM),	(P), 2 mg/kg/day prednisolone and 2.5 mg/kg/day azathioprine (P/A), 2 mg/kg/day prednisolone and 1000 mg intravenous cyclophosphamide pulse therapy monthly (P/PC).	to be less efficacious than azathioprine and pulse cyclophosphamide.	Esmaili, Maryam Daneshpazhooh, Mahin Valikhani, Kamran Balighi, Zahra Hallaji, MD, Masoumeh Barzegari, Maryam Akhyani, S. Zahra Ghodsi, Hassan Seirafi, Mohammad-Javad Nazemi Tabrizi, Hossein Mortazavi, and Mostafa Mirshams-Shahshahani, MD	
3	96 patients with mild to moderate pemphigus vulgaris	Mycophenolate mofetil 2 or 3 g/day	Placebo	Mycophenolate mofetil was found to be an efficacious drug.	Stefan Beissert, Daniel Mimouni, Amrinder J. Kanwar, Neil Solomons, Veena Kalia and Grant J. Anhalt.	2010
4	36 pemphigus vulgaris and 11 pemphigus foliaceus patients	Methylprednisolone (1 mg/kg) + Mycophenolate mofetil (3 g/day, 1.5 g twice daily)	Methyl-Prednisolone (1 mg/day)	Combination treatment with methylprednisolone and mycophenolate mofetil showed no advantage over monotherapy treatment with corticosteroids	D. Ioannides, Z. Apalla, E. Lazaridou, D. Rigopoulos	2012
5	86 patients with pemphigus vulgaris from the first stage of previously randomized clinical trial were enrolled	2 mg/kg/day prednisolone + and 2 g/d mycophenolate mofetil	2 mg/kg/day prednisolone, 2 mg/kg/day prednisolone + 2.5 mg/kg/day azathioprine, 2 mg/kg/day prednisolone + 1000 mg intravenous cyclophosphamide pulse therapy monthly.	No therapeutic benefits of oral prednisolone and mycophenolate mofetil was reported.	Esmaili N, Chams-Davstchi C, Valikhani M, Daneshpazhooh M, Toosi S, Karimi A, Mortazavi H.	2014

Table 1: Evaluation Of Efficacy Of Mycophenolate Mofetil In The Management Of Pemphigus Vulgaris As Per PICO.

Search Strategy:- An exhaustive bibliographic search was conducted in PubMed to identify relevant articles. Controlled vocabulary (MeSH terms in PubMed) and free- text terms in the titles and/or abstracts were used to define the search strategy in all databases.

The search strategy developed for PubMed was like –
 Pemphigus vulgaris (MeSH) and Corticosteroids (MeSH)
 Mycophenolate mofetil (MeSH) and Pemphigus vulgaris (MeSH)
 Pemphigus vulgaris (MeSH) and Adjuvant drugs (MeSH).

Data extraction:- Information of the included studies was collected by one of the reviewers (RM) and a second one (AD) cross-checked independently all of the retrieved data. The following data were systematically collected from each included study: publication details (authors, country, and year), sample characteristics (sample size), study methodology (drug used, duration of drug administered, experimental condition) characteristics related to outcomes (relevant findings), and outcome.

Assessment of risk of bias:- It was conducted according to the guidance in Higgins, JPT, Green, S (editors): the Cochrane Handbook for systematic review of Interventions Versions 5.1,0 (updated March 2011) The Cochrane collaboration, 2011.

RESULTS

Table 2 provides the descriptive statistics for complete healing of lesions obtained in 4 studies, along with relative risk ratio difference and weight of each study in the analysis. The estimates of measures of heterogeneity for healing of lesion based on four studies were: $I^2 = 65.84\%$ which showed moderate heterogeneity. The relative risk difference for fixed effects and random effect were 1.005 and 1.041 respectively. However, they showed insignificant effect of treatment, as indicated by p-values of 0.922 and 0.584 for each. (Fig. 2)

Study	Intervention	Controls	Relative risk	95% CI	z	P	Weight (%)	
							Fixed	Random
Beissert S et al.,2006	31/33	24/33	1.292	1.030 to 1.620			12.82	20.03
Chams-Davatchi C et al.,2007	84/120	96/120	0.875	0.755 to 1.014			30.19	27.78
Beissert S et al.,2010	66/96	61/96	1.082	0.883 to 1.325			15.94	22.13
Ioannides D et al.,2012	34/36	33/36	1.03	0.908 to 1.169			41.05	30.06
Total (fixed effects)	215/285	214/285	1.005	0.916 to 1.102	0.098	0.922	100	100
Total (random effects)	215/285	214/285	1.041	0.901 to 1.204	0.547	0.584	100	100

Test for heterogeneity	
Q	8.7832
DF	3
Significance level	P = 0.0323
I^2 (inconsistency)	65.84%
95% CI for I^2	0.00 to 88.36

Table 2: Comparison of complete healing of lesions immediately after completion of treatment across different studies

Fig. 2- The forest plot provides the visualization of relative risk across studies.

Table 3 provides the descriptive statistics for remission obtained in 4 studies, along with relative risk ratio difference and weight of each study in the analysis. The estimates of measures of heterogeneity for remission based on four studies were: $I^2 = 71.02\%$ which showed considerable heterogeneity. The relative risk difference for fixed effects and random effect were 1.161 and 1.190 respectively. However, they fixed effect showed significant effect of treatment, as indicated by p-values of 0.008 and random effect showed insignificant effect of treatment with p-value of 0.149.(Fig. 3)

Study	Intervention	Controls	Relative risk	95% CI	z	P	Weight (%)	
							Fixed	Random
Beissert S et al., 2006	31/33	24/33	1.292	1.030 to 1.620			19.5	29.26
Chams-Davatchi C et al., 2007	97/120	96/120	1.010	0.892 to 1.145			64.1	36
Beissert S et al., 2010	65/96	43/96	1.512	1.164 to 1.964			14.6	26.82
Ioannides D et al., 2012	9/36	11/36	0.818	0.386 to 1.732			1.78	7.92
Total (fixed effects)	202/285	174/285	1.161	1.039 to 1.297	2.64	0.008	100	100
Total (random effects)	202/285	174/285	1.190	0.940 to 1.506	1.44	0.149	100	100

Test for heterogeneity	
Q	10.3536
DF	3
Significance level	P = 0.0158
I^2 (inconsistency)	71.02%
95% CI for I^2	17.28 to 89.85

Table 3: Comparison of remission of disease after follow up across different studies

Fig. 3- The forest plot provides the visualization of relative risk across studies.

Table 4 provides the descriptive statistics for adverse effect obtained in 3 studies, along with relative risk ratio difference and weight of each study in the analysis. The estimates of measures of heterogeneity for adverse effect based on four studies were: $I^2 = 39.34\%$ which showed low heterogeneity. The relative risk difference for fixed effects and random effect were 1.051 and 0.993 respectively. However, they fixed effect showed insignificant effect of treatment, as indicated by p-values of 0.430 and random effect also showed insignificant effect of treatment with p-value of 0.980. (Fig. 4)

Study	Intervention	Controls	Relative risk	95% CI	z	P	Weight (%)	
							Fixed	Random
Beissert S et al., 2006	6/33	11/33	0.545	0.229 to 1.302			1.1	19.17
Beissert S et al., 2010	91/96	83/96	1.096	1.000 to 1.202			98.15	66.41
Esmaili N et al., 2014	7/36	5/36	1.4	0.490 to 4.003			0.75	14.42
Total (fixed effects)	104/165	99/165	1.051	0.930 to 1.186	0.793	0.430	100	100
Total (random effects)	104/165	99/165	0.993	0.634 to 1.557	-0.029	0.980	100	100

Test for heterogeneity	
Q	3.2971
DF	2
Significance level	P = 0.1923
I^2 (inconsistency)	39.34%
95% CI for I^2	0.00 to 81.21

Table 4: Comparison of adverse effect across different studies**Fig. 4- The forest plot provides the visualization of relative risk across studies**

DISCUSSION

As mortality of patients in pemphigus vulgaris is due to potential treatment complications, researchers have attempted to include adjuvant modalities to increase the efficacy of corticosteroids while reducing their toxicity. Mycophenolate mofetil, an immunosuppressive drug has been found to possess wide therapeutic index with minimal toxicity. However, the data emerging from various studies are confusing. Some case control, cohort studies reported effectiveness of mycophenolate mofetil with pemphigus vulgaris in combination with corticosteroids whereas others did not necessarily corroborate these findings. We have searched electronic database; duplicate articles were removed and eligibility were checked of forty five articles. Finally, meta analysis was carried out on the efficacy of mycophenolate mofetil which included five randomized controlled trials (RCTs) with the three outcome variables in mind i.e

- 1] Complete healing of lesions immediately after treatment
- 2] Remission of disease after follow up
- 3] Adverse effects of mycophenolate mofetil.

Out of which four studies by Beissert S et al 2006,⁽⁷⁾ Chams-Davatchi C et al 2007,⁽¹²⁾ Beissert S et al 2010,⁽⁸⁾ Ioannides D et al 2012⁽¹³⁾ were included for first and second outcomes. One study by Esmaili N et al 2014⁽³⁾ has a follow up report of extended 1 year of an already included trial combined with the initial trial data, so not included. However, in the third outcome variable analysis, that follow up study was included as it comprised of minor and major recurrences and adverse effect showed by the patients. Among these trials, two trials have included patients with recently diagnosed disease with no prior treatment with systemic corticosteroids or immunosuppressive drugs; two trials did not specify disease duration and one trial was a follow up. Reported baseline disease ranged from mild to moderate as specified by one trial and four trials did not specify disease severity.

Following section has discussed the meta analysis of studies in context to outcome variables

- 1] **Complete healing of lesions immediately after completion of treatment**– Complete healing of lesions was reported in 4 trials by Beissert S et al 2006,⁽⁷⁾ Chams-Davatchi C et al 2007,⁽¹²⁾ Beissert S et al 2010,⁽⁸⁾ Ioannides D et al 2012⁽¹³⁾. Mycophenolate mofetil was not associated with an increase in the proportion of patients with complete healing of lesions. Chance of event occurring is highest in intervention i.e mycophenolate mofetil group as compared to the control group in the study by Beissert S et al 2006,⁽⁷⁾ Beissert S et al 2010⁽⁸⁾ and Ioannides D et al 2012⁽¹³⁾ which means more complete healing of lesions is seen in the mycophenolate group while it is highest for control group in the study by Chams-Davatchi C et al 2007⁽¹²⁾ where 96 patients showed complete healing of lesions than in 84 patients in the mycophenolate mofetil group. Chance of event occurring is same for both the mycophenolate mofetil and control group, hence insignificant difference was found across different studies by fixed effects and random effects
- 2] **Remission of disease after follow up** - Remission of disease after follow up was reported in 4 trials by Beissert S et al 2006,⁽⁷⁾ Chams-Davatchi C et al 2007,⁽¹²⁾ Beissert S et al 2010⁽⁸⁾ and Ioannides D et al 2012⁽¹³⁾. Mycophenolate mofetil was associated with an increase in the proportion of patients showing remission of disease after follow up. In study by Beissert S et al 2006,⁽⁷⁾ Chams-Davatchi C et al 2007⁽¹²⁾ and Beissert S et al 2010⁽⁸⁾, more remission of disease is seen in the mycophenolate group as chance of event occurring is highest in intervention i.e mycophenolate mofetil group as compared to the control group and it is highest for control group in the study by Ioannides D et al 2012⁽¹³⁾. Significant P value of 0.008 across different studies is found for total fixed effects for remission of disease and as the chance of event occurring in both mycophenolate group and control group is same, insignificant difference is found by random effect.
- 3] **Adverse effect** – Adverse effect was reported in 3 trials by Beissert S et al 2006,⁽⁷⁾ Beissert S et al 2010⁽⁸⁾ and Esmaili N et al 2014⁽³⁾. Mycophenolate mofetil was not associated with an increase in the proportion of patients showing adverse effect. Chance of event occurring is highest in intervention i.e mycophenolate mofetil group as compared to the control group in the study by Beissert S et al 2010,⁽⁸⁾ and Esmaili N et al 2014⁽³⁾ which means less adverse effects were found in the mycophenolate group while it is highest for control group in the study by Beissert S et al 2006⁽⁷⁾. Chance of event occurring is same for both the mycophenolate mofetil and control group, hence insignificant difference was found across different studies by fixed effects and random effects. Combination therapy of mycophenolate mofetil with corticosteroid was found to help lower initial steroid dose without relapse, faster reduction of steroid dose as well as much less final maintenance dose and remission of disease in patients but its efficacy in the treatment of pemphigus vulgaris was not much significant. Even so, mycophenolate mofetil appears to have a wide therapeutic index and lacks significant organ toxicity.

Limitations

RCTs are few in the literature so as to be included in our meta analysis. Patient population, disease severity and outcome definitions were not the same across studies. Also, the protocol for escalation and tapering of corticosteroids varied between studies, which could have impacted the study outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Numerous treatment modalities that have been implicated to cure pemphigus such as the use of immunosuppressive agents, anti-inflammatory agents and immunomodulators with the most recent treatment being the rituximab. Still present, corticosteroids are the fundamental drugs in the management of pemphigus vulgaris, the treatment regimen is modified with the addition of various adjuvant drugs according to the disease severity.

As there is no standard treatment of pemphigus fulfilling the criteria of evidence-based medicine till date, our systematic review and meta analysis suggests that mycophenolate mofetil is equally effective in the management of pemphigus vulgaris with complete remission and less adverse effects. More extensive clinical trials involving a greater number of cases and including more parameters are necessary to come to a final conclusion about a particular modality in the management of pemphigus vulgaris. So, it can be the potential agent in the management of pemphigus vulgaris.

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